

Effects of PowToon-Application ... (Usman, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073698>

Effects of PowToon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in North-Central, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Effects of Powtoon application video on achievement and retention among pre-service Geography teachers in North Central, Nigeria. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The target population for this study was 1,163 pre-service Geography teachers, during the 2023/2024 academic session in North Central and One-fifty-One (151) were sampled for the study. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. Two experts validated the research instrument used for the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha and 0.735 reliability, index was obtained. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Based on the findings, the study revealed that, utilization of Powtoon application videos in teaching of Geomorphology concepts enhanced students' performance than those exposed to conventional method of teaching. Based on the findings, it was further recommended among others that Geography teachers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon application videos as it promotes flexible learning and independent learning.

Keywords: Powtoon Application, Achievement, Retention and Geomorphology

Introduction

Over the last two decades, there have been advancements in digital technology, starting from the emergence of simple tools to the highly sophisticated devices and applications used tremendously in performing different task and functions in all sectors of the economy. Globally, there is virtually no sector that has not experienced technological shift from traditional ways of doing things to digitization. Technology has permeated almost all human endeavors, and its importance has cut across all facets of life (Ibrahim *et al*, 2024). The advancement in digital technology and the rate at which they emerge has driven innovation and new applications that touch our lives in different and often profound ways, thus, providing numerous opportunities and aspiration associated with digitalization (Singh 2021). The world has become increasingly more digital and ever more dependent on technological innovations.

Technological innovation is increasingly penetrating into education and skill domain with technology gradually being used to deliver education (instruction) knowledge and skill in new and invasive ways, therefore resulting in digital learning. Technology has transformed teaching and learning to be more student-centered through the incorporation of technology in education (Ibrahim *et al*, 2024). Technology is the principal delivery system of information particularly in online courses therefore, serving as a foundation for teaching and has encouraged instructors to device various means of teaching relevant course contents with applications, such as Powtoon.

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Powtoon is an online presentation software tool that allows individuals to create free and professional animated video explainers/messages and presentations as a substitute for PowerPoint. Powtoon is one of numerous application service providers for effortlessly creating learning material. Basri (2021), (Singh, 2020; Puspitarini and Hanif, 2019) It is a web-based application for quickly creating animated cartoons and video presentations. (Ashari, 2018). Powtoon is an e-Tool that creates animated videos for personal, educational, professional use, it is a free, web-based (with options to upgrade), user-friendly software that creates presentations via three simple and easy steps: writing a script, recording a voiceover, and adding visuals. This application can help teachers make animated exposures with features like handwriting animation, cartoon animation, and more vibrant transition effects with easy timing Basri (2021). (Balwant and Doon, 2021; Puspitarini and Hanif, 2019). The Powtoon application operates in a similar way to PowerPoint, in that it creates slides with teaching content. The distinction is in the animated character features, wherein Powtoon there are many different sorts of engaging animations that can assist the information to be presented, making it more interesting to deliver. Powtoon creates exposures that have animated features including handwriting animations, cartoon animations, and more vibrant transition effects and easy timing, most especially in courses such as Geography.

Geography is a subject that enable us to comprehend the Earth from a spatial viewpoint, by offering an organized structure about the world that surrounds us (Filgona, et al., 2017). The knowledge of geography is not only important and useful to the learners, but to everyone who seeks to cope with the ever-changing trends of our environment. The earth being the theatre where virtually all human activities take place is the focus of geographical study. Therefore, it is plausible that man knows about the nature and phenomenon on earth and the consequences of the interactions between man and his physical environment. In addition, the teaching of geography offers a unique means of furthering inquiry and high intellectual growth in students. Furthermore, studies have revealed that learning is facilitated as animation create positive attitude among the learners leading to positive learning outcomes. It can be in terms of their achievement and retention.

Academic achievement is the extent to which the learner or instructor or institution has attained their short- or long-term goals. Much researches in the recent years have focused on identifying the key factors that promotes academic achievement among student. The explosion of ICT has influenced the development of the society, in addition, Although, Powtoon is considered as a powerful and useful tool used in teaching and learning, Powtoon instructional videos just like other instructional application and technologies has inarguably assisted in high retention rate among geography students. Several studies have reported that multimedia can improve academic achievement (Moussa-Inaty, et al., 2019;), Similarly, Suyatna et al. (2017) revealed that enhanced achievement may also lead to students' ability to retain concepts better in a given task.

Retention is an ability to remember or recognize the content that has been learned or experienced or the ability to acquire and comprehend the knowledge as well as remember the content that has been mastered is an important issue in teaching and learning. Learning is effective when knowledge has been transferred into new situation. Retention is the ability to acquire and comprehend the knowledge of physical geography (Filgona, et al (2017). Studies have shown that student taught using other instructional application and technologies other than lecture method achieve greater material retention.

Statement of the Research Problem:

In spite of the usage of various effective interactive technologies and strategies such as the use of cartoons, pictures, illustrations, graphics among others, at various times to improve students' performance especially in physical Geography, the performances have persisted as shown by the semester results. The semester results of pre-service teachers in Geomorphology from Niger State College of Education Minna revealed from 2018/2023, that students' performance has been poor. However, several factors have been attributed to the dismal performance of pre-service teachers in the area of Geomorphology such as abstractness, inadequate use of technologies such as videos and the laxity on the part of the lecturers and the students. Consequently, upon the above, the need to alleviate the difficulties of abstraction and improve students' performance in physical Geography has informed and encouraged the use of advanced technologies such as Powtoon instructional videos, which are alternative ways to deliver relevant course content. Powtoon instructional videos are proven to be fun –based videos which attract the attention of the learners as well as improve the creative skill and understanding of the learners' on difficult and abstract concept. The use of videos (Powtoon) eliminates long passive teaching and rote learning that are associated with traditional methods of teaching and clears pre- service teachers misconception on what seems to be, to what it is, more so, these videos engages the cognitive/ mental ability of the learner and assist in retaining knowledge on content taught effectively. As a result, the researcher sought to investigate the Effects of Powtoon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-Central, Nigeria

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Objectives of the study:

The aim of the study was to investigate the Effects of Powtoon-Application-Videos on Achievement and Retention in Geomorphology among Colleges of Education pre-service teachers in North-Central, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to:

1. Develop Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on Geography (Geomorphology) concepts.
2. Determine the effects of Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on pre-service Geography teachers' academic achievement in Geomorphology.
3. Investigate the effects of Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos on pre-service Geography teachers' retention in Geomorphology.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What are the strategies in the development of Powtoon application videos for teaching and learning of Geomorphology among pre-service Geography teachers in North-central Nigeria?
2. What are the differences in the mean academic achievement score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method?
3. What are the differences in the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method?

Hypotheses:

The following null research hypotheses were formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance;

HO₁. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos.

HO₂. There is no significant difference in the retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon and Animato-generated instructional videos

Methodology

The study adopted experimental research design. The research design that was adopted for this study is Quasi-experimental experimental design using the pretest, posttest non-equivalent group. The variables of the study included achievement, retention, attitude and Powtoon. The targeted population for the study comprises of 782 pre-service geography teachers in north central. The entire population was used for the study because of the manageable size of the population. The research instruments that were used for the study are: Treatment instruments and test instruments. The instruments were validated by experts in Geography, Educational Technology, in Federal University of Technology, Minna psychology and Computer Studies in College of Education Minna. In order to determine the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted using 15 students who were part of the population but that did not participate in the main study. The data collected was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula (PPMC) and a reliability coefficient of 0.735 and 0, 749, were obtained respectively. Mean and standard deviation were the descriptive statistics used to analyze the data collected for the purpose of answering the three research questions raised. A decision mean score of 3.00 was used. Every item with a mean score below 3.00 was considered as Disagree while an item with mean scores of 3.00 and above was considered as Agree. Similarly, inferential statistics was used to test the six null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance using (Z-Test) at pretest. If a significant difference exists at pretest between the groups, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used at posttest to normalize the pre-existing group differences.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the strategies in the development of Powtoon application videos for teaching and learning of Geomorphology among pre-service Geography teachers in North-central Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Powtoon application video was developed with the aid of ADDIE Model by the researcher through the following strategies/steps.

Step1: Planning and identifying geomorphology concept (mountains, plateau and plains) as well as creating a storyboard.

Step 2: Designing tips, visuals, color scheme font and engagement text on geomorphology concepts.

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Step 3: Developing/Creating the Powtoon video by signing up/ creating an account on Powtoon, selecting a template adding slides, adding content, text images, animations voice over and transitions.

Step 4: Implementing the video, by Reviewing the video and sharing it to the learners to view the content of the video.

Step 5: Evaluating the video to obtain the feedbacks after sharing it for the learners.

Research Question 2: What is the mean achievement score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method? To answer this research question, descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation was used.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of pretest and posttest achievement scores of experimental group and control group.

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental Group	120	8.37	3.021	21.71	3.258	13.34
Control group	31	10.29	3.143	19.13	3.703	8.84

Key: X=Mean SD=Standard Deviations, N= Number in Samples

Table 1 displays the mean and standard deviation of experimental group treated with Powtoon application video and control group taught with lecture method at pretest and posttest level. The mean achievement scores of experimental group in the posttest was higher with a mean score of (M=21.71, SD=3.258) than the pretest mean score of (M=8.37, SD=3.021) indicating a major change in their achievement obtained from the pretest posttest mean differences (13.34) for the experimental group. Similarly, in the control group, the mean achievement scores on the posttest was higher (M= 19.13, SD = 3.703) than the pretest mean score of (M=10.29, SD=3.143) indicating a major change in their achievement obtained from the pretest posttest mean differences (8.84) for the control group. Thus, there is a difference in the achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers' taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application video achieving higher than those taught with to lecture method.

Research Question 3: What is the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and those exposed to conventional method? To answer this research question, descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of posttest and retention test scores of experimental group and control group.

Group	N	Posttest		Retention		Mean differences
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental Group	120	21.71	3.258	19.32	2.868	2.39
Control Group	31	19.13	3.703	17.37	2.500	1.76

Key: X=Mean SD=Standard Deviations, N= Number in Samples

Table 2 displays the mean and standard deviation of experimental group treated with Powtoon application video and control group taught with lecture method at posttest and retention test. The mean retention scores of students for the experimental group was higher (M=19.32, SD=2.868) than the posttest score (M=21.71, SD= 3.258). The mean difference was (2.39) indicating a substantial loss in their retention. For the control group, the mean retention scores were also lower (M=17.37, SD=2.500) than the posttest score (M=19.13, SD=3.703). The mean difference was (1.76) indicating a loss in their retention. The finding revealed that there is a difference in the mean retention score of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application video and lecture method, with students exposed to Powtoon application video retaining higher than those in the control group.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method.

Table 3: ANOVA comparison of the posttest mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	163.521	1	163.521	12.493	0.001
Within Groups	1950.254	149	13.089		
Total	2113.775	150			

Table 3: presents the result of an ANOVA conducted to compare the posttest mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group. The ANOVA was used to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the

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mean achievement scores between these two experimental groups the between groups variation representing the differences in mean achievement scores between experimental group and control group, revealed that there was statistically significant difference $F(12,493) = 0.001, p < 0.05$ indicating a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method, the hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method differs significantly in their mean achievements.

H₀₂. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method.

Table 4: ANOVA comparison of the retention mean scores of experimental group and control group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	94.247	1	94.247	14.175	0.000
Within Groups	990.641	149	6.649		
Total	1084.887	150			

Significant at P<0.05

Table 4: presents the result of an ANOVA conducted to compare the retention mean achievement scores of experimental group and control group. The ANOVA was used to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the mean retention scores between these two groups. The between groups' variation representing the differences in mean achievement scores between experimental group and control group. The table revealed that $F = 14.175, \text{sig-VALUE} = .000$ AT $P > 0.05$, indicating a significant difference in the mean retention scores of pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method, the hypothesis is also rejected. This implies that pre-service Geography teachers taught Geomorphology using Powtoon application videos and conventional method differs significantly in their mean retention.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings, it was revealed that using Powtoon application video and lecture method were all effective in improving students' retention in Geomorphology but students exposed to Powtoon application video retaining higher than those in the control group. This finding affirmed the assertions of Puspitarini, et al., (2018) whose findings indicated that using Powtoon in teaching enhance students' performance than expository method of teaching. The reason of this finding could be to the fact that Powtoon presentations enabled students to demonstrate collaborative learning and creativity in the design and organization of ideas. Both collaboration and creativity are essential skills for the 21st century learners. Basri and Fadli (2021) also found that the use of the Powtoon Application could increase students' learning motivation where the mean value increased significantly and the increase in motivation of the experimental group was higher than the control group. The finding of this study corroborates with the findings of Ashari (2018) which revealed that Powtoon is one of the software for creating animated features, including handwriting animations, cartoon animations, and more vibrant transition effects and easy timing, so this Powtoon application is containing material, combined with animations and transitions to make it more exciting and convenient.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion above, Powtoon application video media is developed on the basis of learning in the classroom which still uses many lecture methods, especially on memorizing material, learning resources and learning media using textbooks, electronic school books (BSE), images and maps and not yet utilized facilities in schools such as the internet, laptops, LCDs and projectors optimally. The study revealed that using Powtoon instructional video is highly effective in improving students' retention in Geomorphology and as such Powtoon videos should be blended with other teaching method such as lecture method for effective learning to take place. Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made to improve students' performance in Geography: Geography lecturers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon application videos as it promotes flexible learning, autonomous and independent learning. Geography lecturers should motivate students to learn Geography using Powtoon application videos Technology to improve their performances generally. Global system for Mobile Network (GSM) should improve on their services for a steady network to be achieved especially in rural areas.

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Recommendations

1. Geography lecturers should utilize and encourage students on the use of Powtoon and Animoto instructional videos Technology as it promotes flexible learning, autonomous and independent learning.
2. Geography lecturers should motivate learner to learn Geography using Powtoon application videos to improve their performances generally.

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